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**PERFORMANCE STYLES AND LITERARY DEVICES IN HƏBA TRADITIONAL
DIRGES**

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Abstract

Songs are among the cultural heritages that Høba ethnic group transmits from one generation to another. It has been observed in the last three decades that Høba funeral songs are seriously threatened by the presence of foreign religious funeral songs. As 95% of the tribe has embraced either Christianity or Islam, traditional funeral songs are hardly performed at funeral ceremonies. In this study, performance style and literary devices are investigated with the view to revitalize and preserve the fast fading cultural values embodied in funeral songs. The corpus of the study consists of two dirges recorded at traditional funeral ceremony of the author's grandmother in 1995. Being non-numerical data, the selected dirges were analysed qualitatively. The result showed that Høba dirges have formal organisational structures-opening, middle and ending. The outcome of the study also showed that informal style is predominantly used in the performance of the two dirges. Both dirges have formal organizational structures which are opening, middle and closing. The analysis of the syntactic showed that the performers used simple sentences intertwined with complex sentences. Also, it was uncovered that informal style was predominantly used by the performers in expressing their grief over the loss of their love ones.

Informal expressions were prevalent in the two texts literary devices such as imageries, symbolisms, metaphors, similes, allusions, and repetitions among others were employed in the expression of the griefs. These literary devices dress the content of the dirges and convey clearly the performers' feelings of grief better.

Key words: Folksongs, dirges, lexis, syntactic features and literary devices

Introduction

Songs are among the verbal cultures that ethnic groups pass down from one generation to another. Every ethnic group has folksongs embodying its cultural heritages. In Həba community, different songs are performed for different purposes in different contexts. The folksongs performed by Həba prior to their contact with foreign cultures include work songs, funeral songs, initiation or passage to adulthood songs, hunting songs, love songs, abuse and social commentary among others. The themes of the songs reflect their contexts of performance.

Traditional funeral songs among the Həba were performed as part of funeral proceedings that the tribe carry out before and after burying the dead. The funeral proceedings however, differ depending on the age, gender and religion of the deceased. Traditional dirges were performed in Həba community by close female relations to mourn the dead. They were performed when the dead were laid in state awaiting burial and during later funeral ceremonies.

The contact of Həba with Western cultures, especially education and religion has negatively affected their funeral proceedings. Prior to the people's contact with Western Education, Christianity and Islam, the dead were buried according to customs and traditions. Dirges were performed in *nya Həba* (Həba language) during funeral proceedings. Female close relations of the deceased usually sang dirges to mourn the dead, when a corpse was laid in state awaiting burial and during two subsequent funeral rites organised to mark the transition of the dead from the land of the living to the great beyond. The dirges were solo because each performing woman expressed her personal griefs and emotional experiences, while sitting by the corpse, moving round it or round the house. Performing dirges round the corpse or the house of the deceased as

maintained by Finnegan (2012) is common in African societies. Up to this day, this is still common among the Həba, especially at Christian funerals.

Over the years, however, it has been observed that the performance of traditional dirges among the Həba is fast fading away. The fading of the performance of traditional dirges in Həba language is attributed to the fact that 95 % of the people have embraced either Christianity or Islam. In place of the traditional dirges which were performed by the close female relations, funeral songs with various themes of death drawn from Christianity or Islam are performed. For the Christians, English funeral songs from hymns books are sung alongside locally composed ones by subgroups in churches such as the women fellowship, the choir, and the New Life for All group known *in Hausa as Kungiyar Mawakan Sabon Rai Don Kowa*.

Traditional dirges and folksongs of the Həba in general need to be revitalized and preserved, lest they go extinct. In recent times, efforts have been made to form various groups and associations aiming at revitalizing, promoting and preserving the cultural heritages of Həba. These include Həba revitalization initiative (HRI), the Həba Youth Council (HYC), Həba Language Development Association (HLDA), and Həba Traditional Gospel Singers (HTGS) among others. The two traditional funeral dirges analysed in this study were performed at the final funeral ceremony of the author's paternal grandmother in 1995. The aim is to complement the current efforts of the Həba scholars towards revitalizing and preserving their cultural heritage. The present day Həba dirges are not selected because this study aims to revitalize and preserve the threatened folksongs.

Brief on Həba funeral rites

The Həba are predominantly found in Hong Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. Həba is the aboriginal name of the tribe which was erroneously codified by British colonial administrators as Kilba. However, the name ‘Həba’ is now maintained in the Həba orthography published by the Nigerian Educational and Development and Research Council (NEDRC) in 2022 and launched by the Həba Language Development Association in 2024

Death in Həba community is followed by some rites immediately it occurs. Some are performed immediate somebody passes on which culminates in burial ceremony. Others are performed after burial depending on the age of the deceased and the season in which the death occurred. The children are buried immediately and no funeral ceremonies are organized later. This is because the death of children is more painful and heart breaking than the death of the adults. The people believe that leaving the dead bodies of the children for long increases their pain. Members of the immediate families, however, would sit with the parents of the deceased to receive condolence messages. In terms of the death of a youth, a ceremony called *sədəfa* would be organized a month or two later. People older than the deceased would hardly be in attendance. Even if they attend, they would not partake in drinking the locally brewed beer or the prepared food.

People that died when the rainy season had set in would have their funeral ceremonies differed to be performed in the dry season from February to April. A grave cleansing ceremony called *dlədəu* would be organised in July or November in the case of male folks to weed off the grass that might have grown on the grave and in August or October in the case of female folk. The ceremony was in the form of a vigil. The grave was hoed and libations prepared from local yeast and the unpressed beer called *ibir mbadla* was poured into very shallow curve made on the grave. The libations and the beer were considered as the shares of the deceased and the ancestors. Drumming, singing and dancing would begin between 7.00 and 8.00 pm till about 7.00 am the

following day. At the end of this ceremony, relations would fix the month and the day of the last funeral.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on the theoretical framework of literary stylistic. Literary stylistics focuses on scientific interpretation of literary texts using linguistic methods. It focuses on aesthetics (beauty of language) and their effects on the reader rather the forms of the language. Leech and Short (2007) are of the view that literary stylistics has implicitly or explicitly the goal of explaining the relation of language and artistic function. Distinguishing between the linguist's and literary critic's viewpoints, Leech and Short observe that 'From the linguist's angle, it is 'Why does the author here choose this form of expression?' From the literary critic's viewpoint, it is 'How is such-and-such an aesthetic effect achieved through language?' In this regard, author's distinctive use of language which includes diction or choice of words, syntactic structures and stylistic devices constitute focal points of analysis.

Artistic functions of language in poetic texts are centred on the expression of inner feelings/emotions through the application of different linguistic and literary devices. Bossan(2015) opines that the interpretation of a text to uncover the beauty or aesthetic side of language and how it is used to creatively capture reality is one of the chief aim of literary stylistics. In the study of oral literature texts, literary stylistics can be applied to investigate how authors use language in a sociocultural context to express inner feelings and emotions. The application of literary stylistics as analytical framework to the interpretation of dirges will not only help to uncover the cultural and historical background of texts but also the meanings underlying the author's language use.

Conceptual clarification

Style in linguistics refers to the way language is selected by a speaker or writer to create effects on the audience. The choice of language to create effects encompasses lexical, grammatical and literary devices. Leech and Short (2007) define style as the use of language by a given person in a given context for a given purpose. A comprehensive study of style as further pointed out by Leech and Short covers both linguistic and non-linguistic features of a text. Linguistic features include lexical, grammatical, phonological and graphological features, while non-linguistic factors encompass the context, the purpose and participants. Similarly, in their classical book, *Investigating English Style*, Crystal and Davy define the term 'style' as some or all the linguistic habits shared by a group of people at a time or over a period of time. Style in this sense is determined by the contexts in which language is used by a given people. According to Crystal and Davy, style can also be observed in unique way an individual used language in a given context. In the context of the study at hand, style would be investigated in terms of the unique way the dirge performers used language to express their griefs and celebrate the life of the deceased.

Akporobaro(2006) points out that oral literature, especially oral poetic compositions, very often, reveal a stylised use of diction and syntax. Elaborating on this assertion, Akporobaro maintains that the chosen words, the order, rate and patterns in which they occur are very often different from the normal mode of speech. The study of style in poetic composition in this sense is the investigation of the artistic application of language to achieve desired effect.

A dirge is a song of lament sung to express mourning or grief over the dead of a loved one. In the ancient Həba community, dirges were performed as part of the cultural rites organized before

and after burial. A performer expressed concern over the loss and brought to memory the good deeds and attributes of the deceased. Olanrewaju & Ajoke (n.d) define dirge as a song of lamentation intended to provide memories of the deceased. Its mournful and solemn aspect make it associated with funeral; hence, the term dirge. A dirge as further explained by these authors is characterized by themes of isolation, loneliness, and death. Being a song, that is sung at funerals, the speaker piles on images of nature upon another to describe the grief he feels. In Həba community, the contents of dirges differ from one clan to another. Each of the clans forming the tribe has its praise epithets which are employed by the performers to pay tributes to the deceased.

A dirge according to Moancha (2019) is primarily a song intended to accompany a funeral. In Həba land, the language and content of dirges sung at a given funeral used to be similar. This is because the central theme is the dead and his ancestors/lineage. Similarly, Akporobaro (2006) maintains that in several societies like the Akan, Ewe and Urhobo, the dirge is not just formless cry of bereavement. It is a highly stylistic form of expression that is governed by specific poetic recitative in a determinate form and performance procedure. In a similar way, Poem analysis (2024) explains that dirges are short lyrical poems that are written after the death of someone. In Həba community, dirges are composed and sung spontaneously. The performing women are close relations who know almost every sparkling attribute of the deceased. Dirges as argued by *Novir glossary* (2024) may be used to express the speaker's grief, the grief experienced by others or the understanding of who a deceased was. *Novir glossary* explains further that in creative writing, a dirge refers to a mournful song or piece of music that is often used to create a sorrowful or melancholic tone in literature, serving as reflection of loss, grief, or death.

Dirges, based on these definitions are performed to mourn the death of someone. The focal point is the deceased and often his lineage or ancestors. In many communities in Nigeria, dirges are performed as part of either burial or funeral rites. Tobalase (2014) for instance, maintains that funeral dirges are performed before or after the burial rites of an Awori man, woman or titled chief. Similarly, in a similar way, Finnegan (2012) explains that among the Akan-speaking peoples of southern Ghana, dirges form just one among their much poetry. Finnegan further maintains that dirges are sung or intoned by women as part of the public mourning during funerals. Among the Həba in Adamawa State of Nigeria women sing dirges for the period a corpse lies in state.

Methodology

The corpus for this study consists of two traditional dirges. The dirges were recorded at a live performance during the final funeral ceremony of the author's grandmother in 1995. This is to say that the primary data were obtained through participant observation and recording since the author participated fully in the funeral proceedings. The recorded songs were played, transcribed in Həba language, translated into English and subjected to analysis qualitatively. The two dirges were purposively selected because they were performed by elderly women having adequate knowledge of the sociocultural background of the deceased and the Həba customs and traditions. The scope was limited two dirges in order to ensure comprehensive and in-depth analysis. In the course of analysis, excerpts from the two texts were used to support the description of each identified stylistically distinctive features.

Analysis and Discussion

In this section, the two dirges forming the corpus for the study are analysed and discussed. The analysis focuses on the performance styles and literary devices employed by the performers of the selected dirges to express their griefs and celebrate the life of the deceased person.

Performance styles

Həba traditional dirges were performed by women when a corpse was laid in state and during later funeral ceremonies. The performers used to sit close to the corpse or walk slowly around the hut of the deceased while expressing their griefs. A widow may also wake up at dawn and go to the hut of her deceased husband to lament the death, or when doing domestic works like washing utensils, sweeping or grinding on stone mill. A widow stops performing immediately the final funeral rite called *tiwi* is performed. The two dirges analysed have formal organizational structures: the opening, the middle and the closing. The opening styles of the two texts are different. Text 1 opens with abrupt shower of praises as could be seen below.

Par vui, par kudzam,	Night rain, torrential rain
Amaya, ka nardā ma?	Listen, won't you tell me
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya.	Torrential rain the brings fortune
Amaya! Ka nardā ma?	Listen, won't you tell me?

The metaphorical names night rain and torrential rain connote heroic figure. In this context, the performer compares the disastrous exit of the deceased to the disaster caused by night and torrential rains. The performer laments the sudden death of her father. This is suggested by the rhetorical question, 'won't you tell me?' Həba people use the metaphor 'night rain' as praise of the fearless and daring people. Text II opens with ideophones to provoke the mourner's thoughts and gain sympathy.

Ah-yi-yi, maa nə əna sal na?	Ah-yi-yi, why like this, man?
Bəra wula chiwar ku ving wa	That there is elephant in your room
Gima, əngə ya	Beloved, hear it
Ngatə məoal kwa tsadə na zər wa	Hear məoal sliding of a child
Gima,əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.

The ideophones at the beginning of the rhetorical question in the excerpt above convey sensory experience. This style of opening is used a technique for calling the attention of the audience. The performer questioned why the dead occurred so sudden. The middle of both songs embodies different expressions of griefs and praises. The slow tempo of both texts is in accordance with the mourning mood and feelings of the performers as well as the audience. The excerpt from text I is an example.

Ma ko biya ja ada təl gəuda ya.	When are stepping out father, King of lance
Vame kwa nyi	Suitor of his daughter
Par vui markər nya ki,	Nightrain, three gates
tsadər dzadə ja ma piya tama	Shift a little we lie together

The slow tempo makes the dirges terse. As could be seen above, the performer expresses her griefs effectively and concisely in forms of speech delivery. In the first three lines, she uses metaphors in singing the praise of the deceased. The middle of text II likewise expresses grief and praise.

Mayo dlaa kər na ngya na, gima əngə ya	When I ponder over this life, beloved hear it
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Ma shi jawar nya gundiri hi Hwang ya?	Shall we go up to woo Hong king makers?
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Mo shi təkə tə gwarara bəl ya?	We shall go up to share and dozen returns?
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear

The excerpt from text II above alludes to royalty. Wooing king makers and presenting excessive gifts suggest that the deceased is from a royal family. The rhetorical questions provoke the mourners' thoughts and create dramatic effects. This is because the mourners who might have forgotten that the deceased is a member of a royal family have been minded.

The closings of the two songs are different. Text I end with parallelism which signals the conclusion.

Shal kwa mbəl ngə ya karahona.	A man who shines like the back of black melody bird
Əngə ja ndən wa !	So it is, man.
Sal kwa mbəl ngə ya karahona.	A man who shines like the back of black melody bird
Ada də guma-guma	Father, a handsome man

In the excerpt above, the expressions 'So it is, man and father, a handsome man' are parallel structures. The expression 'so it is, man' also clearly suggests that the performer is making a concluding remark. The expression 'father, a handsome man' similarly serves as the summarising praises. Dirge II on the other hand ends abruptly, leaving the audience in suspense. It evokes curiosity because in the body of the song, the performer brings forth new praise after the refrain 'Beloved, hear it.'

Mode of Delivery

In most cases, dirges in Həba community are solo songs. Close relations like the daughters, cousins, or sisters of the deceased used to perform individually. Dirge I for example was performed by the daughter of the deceased.

Ma ko biya ja ada ya,	tel shafa.	When you are stepping out father, king of Shafa
Ka nardā ma?		Won't you tell me ?
Ma ko biya ja ada təl gəuda ya.		When you are stepping out father, king of lance
Vame kwa nyi		Suitor of his daughter.

In the above excerpt, a daughter is addressing her deceased father. The word 'ada' (father) and the phrase 'vame kwa nyi(suitor of his daughter) suggest clearly that the performer is the daughter of the deceased. In a similar way, the contents of dirge II suggest that it was performed by the wife of the wife of the deceased.

Ah-yi-yi, maa nə əna sal na	Ah-yi-yi, why like this, man?
Bəra wula chiwar ku ving wa	that behold there is an elephant in your room
Gima, əngə ya	Beloved hear it.

The speaker talks to the deceased as if alive. Line one evokes sadness and sympathy. Line two is a symbolic reference to royalty. The word 'elephant' as used in this context is a symbol of aristocracy. Even in the present day Həba community, the term 'chiwar' (elephant) is still used to address dynamic figures.

Informal style

In both dirges, informal style is predominantly used. Informal language is a casual and spontaneous speech such as found in interaction with associates and family members. The performers speak to the dead as if alive, lament over the loss or celebrate the deceased by showering praises. The use of personal pronouns, everyday vocabulary, colloquial expressions and slangs are the common features of informal language which are prevalent in the two texts. The performer of text I for instance evokes intimacy through the use of inclusive pronoun ‘we.’

Ma yo dlaa kər gyana,	When I ponder over this life
Gima, əngə ya.	Beloved, hear it.
Ma mai’i mo shi jawar nya Gundiri hi Hwang wa.	We go up to woo King makers at Hong
Gima əngə ya.	Beloved, hear it.
Mo mai’i mo shi təkə tə gwara blə ya?	We’ll go up to share and dozen returns
Gima, əngə ya	Beloved, hear it

In the excerpt above, the performer speaks to the deceased as if alive. The verb ‘ponder’ in the first sentence expresses the worrisome and perplexing plight of the speaker. In lines 2 and 4, the inclusive subjective personal pronoun ‘we’ expresses the intimacy of the deceased with the speaker. The expressions are colloquial as they are restricted to the funeral context which is only familiar to the members of the speech community. Also, in line 2, the word ‘woo’ refers to the traditional approach of the king makers by the royal family members to gain favour during selection of a king. It was a tradition among the Həba for royal family members who desired to be a king to visit king makers and seek their consent by giving them precious gifts. This is made clear in line 4 by the hyperbolic expression “Shall we go up to share and dozen returns?” The

phrase ‘dozen returns’ refers to excess gifts left after all king makers have been given. This expression presents the deceased as a well to do royal member.

Colloquialism

Colloquialism is another feature of informal language found in both dirges. Examples are contained in the three lines below.

Ma ko biya ja ada ya, t̄ Shafa	When you are stepping out father, King of Shafa
Ka nar d̄a ma?	Won't you tell me?
Ma ko biya ja ada t̄l ḡauda ya	When you are stepping out father, king of lance
Vame kwa nyi	Suitor of his daughter
Par vui,mark̄r nya ki	Night rain, three gates
Tsad̄r dzad̄e ja ma piya tama	Shift, then we lie together

The excerpt above contains colloquial expressions. They are everyday expressions whose meanings are understood only within the H̄aba sociocultural setting. In the first line, the speaker alludes to history to remind the audience about the lineage of the deceased. *Shafa* is an ancient town in the present-day Borno state of Nigeria, where the founder of the two royal houses of H̄aba originated from. The phrasal names such as ‘king of Shafa, night rain, three gates, and suitor of his daughter’ are all praise epithets used to celebrate the deceased. The last line depicts the love of the speaker for the deceased.

The performer of dirge II also used colloquial expressions in the delivery of her dirge.

Bəra wula nguli Hwang təl kwa siya wa	That yonder, the children of Hong Kings are coming.
Gima əngə ya?	Beloved, hear it
Vi nga wur mo shi jawar gundiri ku dziga	Day break, we'll go up to woo the king makers
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Wula Tləlbang-taku kwa dzəva wa	Yonder, Tləlbang horse men are coming
20.Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.

The above excerpt contains everyday expressions but their meanings are rooted in the sociocultural experiences of Həba. 'Children of Hong kings' in line one for instance, refers to the king makers who reside on top of Hong Mountain, the administrative seat of Həba ancient community. Similarly, 'woo the king makers' implies lobbying them for favour during selection of kings.

Metaphors

A metaphor is a figurative expression in which the quality of one thing is transferred onto another. A thing is normally described or referred to as another. Metaphors are direct comparisons of the quality of two different entities to create meaning beyond the literary level. Simpson (2004) refers to a metaphor as the process of mapping between two different conceptual domains. The different domains are known as the target domain and the source domain. The target domain is the topic or concept that you want to describe through the metaphor, while the source domain refers to the concept that you draw upon to create the metaphorical construction. In the excerpt from text I below, the performer referred to the deceased as 'night rain and torrential rain'.

Par vu'i, par kudam!	Night rain, torrential rain
Amaya, ka nar dā ma	Listen, won't you tell me?
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya.	Torrential rain that brings fortune
Amaya, ka nar dā?	Listen, won't you tell me.
Ma ko biya ja ada ya, təl Shafa	When you are stepping out father, king of Shafa
Ka nar dā ma	Listen, won't you tell me?

Night rain in the traditional Həba community was associated with danger. Here, the disastrous exit of an icon is compared to the disaster caused by night and torrential rains. For any disaster it might cause, the victims of night rain remained helpless. Torrential rain in the same vein was considered disastrous. It might result to flood, destruction of farmlands and demolishing of houses of which the victims remained helpless. This metaphor is used in this context to evoke image of the loss of an icon in the community. The performer also referred to the deceased as king of Shafa to remind the audience about the historical background of the deceased. Shafa is an ancient town in the present-day southern Borno. The founders Dawi and Gaya dynasties in Həba community migrated from there

Imageries

Imagery in literature is the use of descriptive language to enable the reader to recall real image or build mental picture. Imagery appeals to the five (5) human senses which are: Visual (appeals to sight), auditory (hearing/sound), olfactory (smell), gustatory (taste), and tactile (touch). kinesthetic (movement) and organic (internal sensation and emotion). In the excerpt from text dirge II below, the performer used auditory and visual images to appeal to the emotions of the audience.

A-yi-yi, ma nə əna sal na?	Ah-yi-yi, why like this, man?
Bəra wula chiwar ku vi ngha.	That behold, an elephant is in your room
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Ngati məoal kwa tsadə na zər wa	Hear məoal sliding off a child
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it

Line 1 of the excerpt is a rhetorical question asked to provoke thoughts and draw the attention of the audience to the worrisome and the perplexing situation caused by the passage of the deceased. The ideophones at the beginning of the question imitate the pains, worries and griefs of the performer. The sounds evoke perplexing and worrisome situation. Line 2 in a like manner evokes memories of royalty. The expression ‘Gima əngə ya’ (Beloved hear it) is an auditory image that appeals to sense of hearing. It is followed by yet another auditory image ‘Hear məoal sliding off a child’. *Məoal* is a section of Hong Mountain where the king makers meet to deliberate on chieftaincy matters. In a similar vein, the performer of dirge 1 used visual and organic imageries to appeal to the emotion of the audience.

Ma ko biya ja ada ya, təl gəda ya	When you are steeping out father, king of lance.
Vame kwanyi	Suitor of his daughter
Par vu’i, makər nya ki	Night rain, three gates
tsadər dzadə, ja, ma piya ta ma	Shift, we lie together

The first line is a visual imagery which evokes the image of a warrior. The third line evokes image of a fearful and dynamic figure. The phrase ‘three gates’ is a cultural metaphor used to describe a polygamist. Polygamists in the then Həba community used to provide more than one

entrance and exit gates to ease the going in and out of the family members. In line 2, the performer used a cultural metaphor ‘suitor of his daughter’ to evoke intimacy. This is an organic imagery which appeals to the internal sensation of the audience to remember the love of the father for the daughter when he was alive. The intimate relationship of the daughter with the father is further expounded by the use of the expression “shift, we lie together”. This is also another organic imagery as it appeals to the internal sensation of the audience.

Symbolism

Symbolism is the figurative or implicit representation of events, people, objects or concepts by words or images. In literature, a symbol is a thing that stands for or represents something else. It could be an object, a mark, an image, a character, a name, or place (Mccrary , and Esparza 2023). The excerpt below from dirge I contains symbolic praise epithets.

Par vui, par kudzam,	Night rain , torrential rain
Amaya, ka nardā ma?	Listen, won’t you tell me ?
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya.	Torrential rain that brings fortune
Amaya, ka nardā ma?	Won’t you tell me?

Night rain among the Həba represents disaster or danger. In this context, the performer uses it to suggest disastrous exit of the deceased and the state of confusion that the family and the community are left in. The performer sees the exit of the deceased as havoc to the family and the community. His death left the family in great confusion. An instance of the use of symbolism is also found in dirge II. ‘Wula Tləlbang-taku kwa dzəva wa. Gima əngə ya’ (Yonder, Tləlbang horse men are coming in). Horse was a symbol of royalty among royal families of the ancient Həba

community. Members of the royal families in those days strive to own horses. Apart from being the symbol of royalty, horses were used in the traditional Həba community for war.

Simile

Simile is a figure of comparison. It is prevalent in the two dirges. Unlike metaphor, which is a direct comparison of two things of different qualities, a simile is an indirect comparison of two things using the word like or as. The following are example of from dirge 1.

Sal kwa mbəl ngə ya kara hona	A man the shines like the back of black melody bird
Ǝngə ja ndən wa	So it is, you man.
Sal kwa mbəl ngə ya kara hona	A man that shines like the back of black melody bird
Ada, ndər guma-guma	Father, a handsome man

Black, shiny skin among the Həba is a thing of pride. It is often used as a praise epithet. The repetition of the simile is meant to achieve emphasis and also creates rhythmic flow. Dirge II opens with rhetorical question simile ‘Ah-yi-yi, maa nə əna sal na?’ (Ah-yi-yi, why like this, man?). This question is asked directly to the corpse as if alive. The ideophones at the beginning of this expression provokes audience’s thoughts and sympathy. Also, in the third stanza, rhetorical question as simile is addressed directly to the deceased. ‘Nakə ngə shingya təl ta’a-ta’a, ngə njang ya?’ (Are you the descendant of chiefs stacked up like festival dishes? This rhetorical question evokes memories of chiefs that ruled from the lineage of the deceased.

The use of rhetorical Questions

Rhetorical questions are found in both dirges. Just like in other contexts, rhetorical questions are asked to draw the attention of the audience, stress a point or persuade the audience. The excerpt from text I below features a repeated rhetorical question.

Par vu'i, par kudzam	Night train, torrential rain
Ama ya ka nar da ma	Listen, won't you tell me?
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya	Torrential rain that brings fortune
Ama ya ka nar da ma	Listen, won't you tell me?

The excerpt is a direct address to the deceased. The performer expresses her grief over the sudden death. The suddenness of the death is suggested by the question 'won't you tell me?' The repetition of this question creates rhythmic flow and evokes sympathy. In addition, this rhetorical question draws the attention of the mourners to the performer's deepest grief and sorrow. In dirge II, two rhetorical questions have been identified.

A-yi-yi, ma na ona sal na?	Ah-yi-yi, why like this, man ?
Mo shi takə tə gwararo bəl ya ?	Shall we go up to share and dozen returns ?

Rhetorical question one contains ideophones which evoke compassion and sympathy. It depicts the perplex situation that the singer is in, state of confusion and worries caused by the death.

The second rhetorical question alludes to Hong, the ancient administrative seat of the Həba people. To go up to share and dozen returns implies that the deceased is a well to do royal family member.

Praise names and praise epithets

Dirges in many African communities combine sadness and grief with praise. In addition to expression of grief, performers often enumerate the achievements and good attributes of the deceased. These are achieved by the use of attributive adjectives to describe the deceased. In dirge I, night rain and torrential rain are praise names used to evoke the iconic traits of the deceased.

Par vui, par kudzam Amaya!	Night rain, torrential rain
Amay, ka nardā ma?	Listen, won't you tell me ?
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya.	Torrential rain that brings fortune
Amaya, ka nardā ma?	Listen, won't you tell me.

These praise names appeal to the feelings and imaginations of the mourners. Both night rain and torrential rain in Həba community connote disaster. They are used as praise epithets to evoke disastrous exit of dynamic community figure. In dirge II, The word 'gima'(beloved) is used to refer to a loved one. This word is commonly used to refer to a fiancée or fiancé but it also connotes anybody dear to someone.

Repetition

Repetition is a strong device used for making emphasis, stressing a point and creating rhythmic flows. It is a figure of speech that shows the logical emphasis that is necessary to attract a reader's attention on a key word or key-phrase in a text. It implies repeating sounds, words, expressions and clauses in a certain succession or even with no particular placement of words, in order to provide emphasis (Kemertelidze & Manjavidze, 2013). This means that repetition can

be at the word, phrase or sentence level. The excerpt from text 1 below contains both lexical and sentential repetitions.

Par vui, par kudzam	Night rain, torrential rain
Amaya, ka nardā ma?	Listen, won't you tell me ?
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya.	Torrential rain the brings fortune
Amaya, ka nardā ma?	Listen, won't you tell me ?

The words night and torrential are used as attributive adjectives to evoke the dynamism of the deceased. The rhetorical question ‘ Ama ya ka nar dā ma’ (Listen, won't you tell me?) is repeated to achieve emphasis and create rhythmic flow. Similarly, in dirge II, the expression ‘Gima əngə ya’ (Beloved hear it), is repeated by the performer after every line. These repetitions create rhythmic flow and suggest grievous mood.

Allusion

An allusion is an implied or indirect reference made to a person, event, place or thing based on the writer's assumption that the reader will know. Irwin (2001) contends that an allusion is bound up with a vital and perennial topic in literary theory, the place of authorial intension in interpretation, and in literature itself allusion has become an increasingly pivotal device. In the two dirges, both singers alluded to historical places, persons, things or events that took place in the past. In dirge II, the performer alluded to Hong, the administrative seat of the ancient Həba chiefdom.

Bəra wula nguli Hwang təl kwa siya wa	That yonder, Hong king makers are coming
Gima, əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Vinga wur mo shi jawu nya gindiri ku Dziga wa	Day break, we go up to woo the king maker
Gima əngə ya	Beloved hear it

The above excerpt is an allusion to history. In the ancient Həba community, the members of the king makers resided at Hong, the administrative seat of the chiefdom. Members of the royal family who desired to be chief visit them at Hong and lobby. The members of the king makers also visited the royal members who were residing in different royal settlements called ‘ngakəu’ for gratification. This is what line one of the excerpt means. The allusion to history in this context is meant to remind the audience that the deceased is a royal member. The excerpt below from II is also an allusion to history.

Ma ko biya ja ada ya, tel shafa.	When you are stepping out father,king of Shafa
Ka nardā ma?	Won't you tell me ?
Ma ko biya ja ada təl gəuda ya.	When you are stepping out father of lance
Vame kwa nyi	Won't you tell me ?

Line 1 of the excerpt alludes to an ancient settlement in Southern Borno where the founders of the two royal dynasties of Həba migrated from. The third line alludes to the ancient strive for territories by members of the ruling family.

Conclusion

Traditional Høba dirges have formal structures-opening, middle and closing. The openings usually draw the attention of the audience, while the middle or body is the main performance. The performers expressed their griefs and sorrows in different modes. The tempo is generally slow which conforms to the sad event. Dirges among the Høba are not performed to the music of any instruments, which makes the expressions of the performer's griefs or feelings clear and concise. The deceased is the focal point in the choice of the delivery styles in both the dirges analysed. The deceased is celebrated through recounting of his/her personal achievements and making reference to the sterling attributes. Praise names and epithets are employed in celebrating the positive life of the deceased.

Informal styles, especially the use of colloquial expressions are common in the dirges. These are every day expressions but the meanings are only clear to those vast in Høba language and familiar with the sociocultural context of the performance. The syntactic features consist mostly of simple sentences intertwined with complex sentences. This style enhances clarity and logical presentations. Literal devices such as metaphors, similes, imageries, symbolisms, allusions and repetitions are prevalent in the two dirges. These literary devices reflect the traditions of the Høba and the social and cultural environments. These literal linguistic cultural heritages need to be preserved lest they go extinct.

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Appendices

Dirge 1

Həba	English
Par vui, par kudzam, Amaya!	Night rain, torrential rain!
Ka nardá ma?	Listens! Won't you tell me?
Par kudzam kwa shili na diya.\	Torrential rain that showers fortune.
Amaya! Ka nardá ma?	Listen! Won't you tell me?
5. Ma ko biya ja ada ya, tel shafa.	When you are going out father, king of Shafa.
Ka nardá ma?	Won't you tell me?
Ma ko biya ja ada təl gəuda ya.	When you are going out father, king of lancers.

<p>Vame kwa nyi Par vui markər nya ki, 10.tsadər dzadə ja ma piya tama</p> <p>Shal kwa mbəl ngə ya karahona. Engə ja ndən wa ! Sal kwa mbəl ngə ya karahona. Ada də guma-guma</p>	<p>Suitor of his daughter Night rain, three exit gates, Shift a little we lie down.</p> <p>A man that shines like the back of black melody bird. So it is, you man!</p> <p>A man that shines like the back of melody bird. Father, a handsome man</p>
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Dirge II

Həba	English
Ah-yi-yi, maa nə əna sal na	Ah-yi-yi, why like this man?
Bəra wula chiwar ku ving wa	That there is an elephant in your room
Gima, əngə ya	Beloved, hear it!
Ngatə məoal kwa tsadə na zər wa	Hear <i>məoal</i> hill sliding the child off
5. Gima,əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Mayo dlaa kər na ngya na, gima əngə ya	When I ponder over this life, beloved, hear it.
Ma shi jawar nya gundiri hi Hwang ya	We'll go up to woo Hong King Makers
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Mo shi təkə tə gwarara bəl ya?	Shall we go up to share and dozens returned?
10. Gima əngə ya	Beloved, here it
Mo shi piya mavi'i nya dziga wa	We'll go up to present slaves at the royal throne
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it.
Nakə ngə shingya təl taaa-taaa, ngə njang ya	Are you the kin of successive chiefs like festival broth?
Gima əngə ya	Beloved hear it
15. Bəra wula nguli Hwang təl kwa siya wa	That there, comes down Hong King Makers
Gima əngə ya?	Belove, hear it Day breaks, we'll up to woo the king makers

Vi nga wur mo shi jawar gundiri ku dziga	Beloved, hear it
Gima əngə ya	
Wula Tləlbang-taku kwa dzəva wa	Yonder, Tləlbang horse men are arriving
20. Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it
Vinga wur mo shi dabiya dzadə da iza	Day breaks we'll go up to assemble under iza tree.
Gima əngə ya	Beloved, hear it
Wula Dazal gəda kwa dabə na Biri	Yonder, Dazal lancers are meeting with Biri
Gima əngə ya	Beloved hear it.
25. Vinga wur njo gwa tsidə dang kər na	Day we'll enter to behead people off
nji	Beloved, hear it.
Gima əngə ya	